

The Effect of Community Empowerment on the Sustainability of Ecotourism Based Tourism through Moderation of Local Wisdom Variables in Bongkasa Village, Abiansemal District

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to understand the role of local wisdom in mediating the relationship between community empowerment and sustainable tourism development. The study was conducted in Bongkasa Tourism Village, using a sample of 100 participants selected through stratified random sampling. The research employed the Partial Least Squares (PLS) approach with a Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) equation model. The findings of this study indicate that local wisdom has a positive influence on sustainable tourism development. Community empowerment also has a positive influence on sustainable tourism development. Furthermore, the local wisdom of the community mediates the relationship between community empowerment and sustainable tourism development. The results of this research can serve as a reference for understanding and making decisions regarding the enhancement of the uniqueness of tourism villages in Bali and Indonesia as a whole.

KEYWORDS: Community and Empowerment, Ecotourism, Local Wisdom, Sustainable Tourism Development.

INTRODUCTION

Ecotourism is a tourism concept that is increasingly being applied, especially in the Province of Bali. This is caused by changes in various industries in running their business, one of which is the tourism industry. The tourism industry in the Province of Bali is demanded to be able to run more efficiently and effectively, when viewed from the conditions of the past pandemic, only a few tourism industries were able to survive, and most of them are industries that rely on native culture and natural wealth, so there is no need large operational costs in its management (Adyatma, 2021). The concept of a tourist village is one example of implementing ecotourism in the tourism industry, in Bali Province in general there are many villages that are classified as tourist villages but have not been able to maximize their potential, several contributing factors include: lack of capital in developing tourist destinations, the community is still not able to see the potential of the village, and only see short-term economic benefits (Cahyani, 2016). In order to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of tourism villages, it is necessary to reformulate the meaning of tourism villages and ecotourism which basically have been applied in social life on the island of Bali.

The main thing in ecotourism is tourism activities that focus on the environment, not only nature, but also the culture and life of the people in these tourism objects. Communities as part of the tourism element must have the ability to manage and map the potential development of their region, and must also have the will to develop and move forward together in achieving joint success related to the development of their village or area of residence (Sulistiyani, 2016). According to Wijayanti (2011) empowerment has the aim of elevating the degree of people who are unable, and elevating their social values from those who are disadvantaged to being successful and occupying a high social structure. The community is expected to have the desire and willingness to move forward, then after that it is continued with the ability to be able to adapt and grow which is obtained through training, teaching, and application of knowledge.

Nilayani (2016) in his research stated that local wisdom is an indicator of the functioning of the rules that apply in society, in this study it is awig-awig. Tri Hita Karana Culture describes the harmonization of human relations with God, nature, and fellow human beings, so that if people want to utilize nature and culture as objects in generating economic benefits in the tourism industry, then people must first understand and be able to apply the concept of local wisdom. Tri Hita Karana so that business continuity in the tourism industry is maintained. The sustainability of a tourist village is the full responsibility of the people who live in the village, the government as a regulator, and investors as a driver of the development of economic activity in the tourism industry. A form of sustainable tourism, its performance must be improved through increased community empowerment in it, because ecotourism is from the community, by the community, and for the community.

Bongkasa Village is a village that belongs to the advanced tourism village category, and has been included in the top 50 Indonesian Tourism Village Awards (ADWI) in 2022 (Kemenparekraf, 2022). Bongkasa Tourism Village is located in Abiansema District, Badung Regency, Bali, with an area of 462.9 hectares with a total of 1,812 households with a total population of 6269 people. Bongkasa Tourism Village has tourism potential for the natural beauty of the environment and Balinese cultural arts which are preserved by the community. Bongkasa Tourism Village has tourism potential such as Ayung River Rafting, Swing, Tracking, Volkswagen Safari Tour, Cycling, and Barong Art Performances, Leather Puppets, Painting, Karawitan, and Dance).

From data published by the Central Bureau of Statistics for Badung Regency (2022), most people in Abiansema District, Badung Regency have income from small and medium trading business activities, providing villa accommodation, restaurants and cafes. Bongkasa Village is one example of a village that has experienced an increase in status from a developing village to an advanced village because it has potential that can be utilized to the fullest. Most of the people, both those who work as farmers, private workers, and entrepreneurs participate in building the village. Some of the research and community service carried out in Bongkasa Village provides an explanation that the very rapid changes in paradigm and technology have not been able to accommodate growth in several aspects of activity, one of which is tourism. Bongkasa Village runs a community-based tourism business, where every member of the community will be involved in business activities, both as owners and management members. However, in practice most of the people only take advantage of natural wealth, and the existence of objects that are already known. This has an impact on not being exposed to several new tourist objects such as trekking, camping and cultural arts tourism objects which are still not officially organized.

From the results of the background discussion, previous research and journals that have been referred to, this research will be carried out in Bongkasa Village, Abiansema District, Badung Regency. The objects of this study are the community and business actors in Bongkasa Village, this study will focus on the magnitude of the influence of community empowerment on the sustainability of ecotourism-based tourism businesses with Tri Hita Karana local culture as a moderating variable in Bongkasa Village, Abiansema District, Badung Regency, Province Bali. The results of this study are expected to be able to provide answers to the relationships between the variables studied so that they can be applied with further research on the development of tourist villages that apply the concept of ecotourism in other areas in the Province of Bali and regions in Indonesia in general.

From research conducted by Lepp (2018) regarding the influence of community empowerment on Sustainable Tourist Development, it was found that the community empowerment variable has a direct and significant effect on the Sustainable Tourist Development variable. H1: Community Empowerment has a positive and significant direct effect on the Sustainable Tourist Development variable. In relation to local wisdom, community empowerment greatly influences how people understand the values and goals of a culture and how to maintain it so that it remains sustainable. Community development aims to build community awareness and willingness to understand the principles of a local wisdom so that its values can be applied not only to business activities, but also to community activities. According to research conducted by Richard (2012) the higher a community group is empowered, the better the local cultural elements will be applied to the sustainability of the tourism village. Communities that are well empowered tend to respect other cultures and people more, and are able to think of long-term goals in preserving historical values in a tourism destination. H2: community development has a direct positive and significant effect on local wisdom

Local wisdom is a culture that teaches humans to live side by side with the environment, this is in line with the concept of ecotourism which is applied to tourism businesses in the Province of Bali. In maintaining the sustainability of the tourism business, the most important thing is to protect nature and the surrounding environment, so that the value of tourist objects can be enjoyed continuously. Windia (2018) in his research explained that people who practice local cultural values have more high productivity in increasing tourist visits. Tourists who visit tourism on an ongoing basis are interested in visiting a tourist object that is still natural and has an original culture that distinguishes it from other areas. H3: Local wisdom has a positive and significant effect on Sustainable Tourist Development. In maintaining the sustainability of tourist destinations, local culture is one of the keys to the success of any regional development program, this is because only the people know their area best compared to those from outside the area. This of course must be strengthened by empowering the community in the area, so that a sustainable tourist area will be created. Omika (2017) in his research explains that community empowerment will have a strong relationship with the stability of the tourism business if it is strengthened by moderation from local cultures owned by the community, so that strengthening relationships will be achieved. H4: community empowerment has a positive effect on the sustainability of tourist development through moderation of local wisdom

RESEARCH METHODS

This research has a broader objective, namely to provide a deeper understanding of the role of local wisdom in mediating the relationship between community empowerment and sustainable tourism development in Bongkasa Village. In a broader context, this research also contributes to providing a valuable reference for decision-making regarding enhancing the uniqueness of tourist villages in Bali and throughout Indonesia. The research method used in this study is a quantitative approach with an associative approach, which makes it possible to measure the magnitude of the influence of these variables through accurate statistical analysis. In an effort to collect comprehensive data, researchers used a mixed approach involving primary data and secondary data. Primary data was obtained through structured interviews and focus group discussions with various stakeholders involved in tourism development in Bongkasa Village, including village heads, local communities and village managers. This interview provides in-depth insight into their views and experiences regarding the concept of local wisdom, community empowerment activities, and the development of sustainable tourism in Bongkasa Village.

In addition, relevant secondary data was also collected from sources such as the Bali Province Central Statistics Agency (BPS) and Badung Regency BPS. This data includes information on the number of tourist objects in Badung Regency, which provides a broader context for the potential for tourism in the region. In carrying out this research, the population that is the focus is the entire community and tourism business managers who are active in Bongkasa Village. From this population, a sample of 100 respondents was selected representing various types of work, including business owners and village tourism business managers. Sampling was carried out using the stratified random sampling method, which ensures that the samples taken reflect the diversity and representation that exists in the population. In measuring the variables studied, the use of a Likert scale from one to four is used to obtain consistent data. This scale provides space for respondents to state the extent to which they agree or disagree with the statements regarding these variables. The inferential statistical approach used in data analysis is Partial Least Squares (PLS) with the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) equation model, which can provide a deeper understanding of the relationship between the variables studied.

In order to develop a research conceptual framework, the complex relationship between community empowerment, local wisdom, and sustainable tourism development in Bongkasa Village will be analyzed. Focus will be given to how local wisdom can mediate the relationship between community empowerment and sustainable tourism development. Thus, this research is expected to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics and potential for sustainable tourism development in Bongkasa Village, as well as provide practical recommendations that can be used by stakeholders to increase the uniqueness and attractiveness of the tourism village. Through this research, it is hoped that the results obtained will make a significant contribution in developing a sustainable tourism development strategy in Bongkasa Village, as well as provide a broader understanding of the potential for sustainable tourism development in Bali and Indonesia as a whole.

Figure 1. Formulation of the Conceptual Framework
Source: 2023 research data

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of this study were processed using the SEM data analysis technique with the Smart PLS program application. This study evaluated 2 models, namely the outer model and the inner model. Evaluation of the measurement model (outer model)

carried out to see whether the questions in the questionnaire are valid and reliable, so that they can proceed to the next stage. While the evaluation of the structural model (inner model) is used to see the level of accuracy in the model used in this study. The indicators in this study are considered valid if the outer loading results in the PLS program are above 0.5 or the t-statistic value is above 1.96. This value indicates the magnitude of the influence of the indicator on the latent variable, the higher the value, the greater the contribution in relation to the latent variable.

In table 1 it can be seen that the three indicators that measure the community empowerment variable (X1) have an outer loading value above 0.5 and are followed by a t-statistic value above 1.96, this means that all indicators are valid indicators to measure the community empowerment variable (X1). on the variable (Y1) all variables have an outer loading value above 0.5 and a t-statistical value of 1.96, which means that all indicators are valid as a measuring tool for local wisdom variables (Y1) . For the sustainable tourism development variable (Y2) the indicator has an outer loading value above 0.5 and is followed by a t-statistic value above 1.96, this means that all indicators forming the variable sustainable tourism development (Y2) are valid.

The results of testing the outer model and the value of the outer loading for each indicator on the three variables can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. OuterModel

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	t-statistics
community empowerment (X1)	X1.1	0.692	7,823
	X1.2	0.521	9,953
	X1.3	0.594	7,936
Local wisdom (Y1)	Y1.1	0.601	7,843
	Y1.2	0.692	8,582
	Y1.3	0.582	7,831
	Y1.4	0.623	8,351
	Y1.5	0.723	8,923
	Y1.6	0.529	7,296
sustainable tourism development (Y2)	Y2.1	0.694	8,452

Source : Data processed, 2023

Composite reliability value is used to see the reliability between the indicator variables and their constituent variables. Reliability composite results are said to be good if they have a test value above 0.70, which means that the relationship between variables and their constituent variables is reliable. The measurement reliability value in this study is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Reliability Test

Variable	Composite Reliability y
community empowerment (X)	0.825
Local Wisdom (Y1)	0.701
Sustainable tourism development (Y2)	0.832

Source : Data processed, 2023

Table 2 shows that the three variables have a composite reliability value of the three latent variables above 0.70, so the variable indicators used to measure these three variables are reliable. To test the research hypothesis, a t-test was carried out on each path which described the relationship between the research variables directly, or partially through mediating variables, while the t-test results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Test Direct and Indirect Influence Through Mediation

Variable Relations	Path Coefficient	t-statistic	Results
X1 with Y1	0.581	5,821	Significant
Y1 with Y2	0.739	6,381	Significant
X1 with Y2 through Y1	0.621	5,082	Significant

Source : Processed data, 202 3

Based on the results of data processing that has been done, it was found that the Community empowerment variable (X1) has a significant effect on the local wisdom variable (Y1) and is indicated by a positive path coefficient of 0.581 with a t-statistic value of 5.821 (greater than 1.96). This shows that Ho is rejected, which means the hypothesis is proven by showing a significant and positive effect between the Community empowerment variable (X1) on local wisdom variables (Y1), so the higher the level of community participation in Community tourism , the higher the community's understanding of local wisdom in managing tourism villages. This opinion is also supported by research conducted by Giampiccoli (2018) which states that Community empowerment is a concept that provides an understanding that community empowerment is important in supporting sustainable tourism activities, so that if people understand and properly apply the Community empowerment concept then indirectly the community will participate in building tourism objects with the goal of common welfare. Regardless of the form of local wisdom that is owned by the community, a sense of belonging must be instilled first, so that through a sense of togetherness an association with shared goals and obligations will emerge, from this a desire will arise to participate in sustainable tourism activities. Amerta (2017) in his research stated that people who live in tourist villages are actors, managers and decision makers in the development of tourist areas. If the community wants to create sustainable tourism, the community must first increase their participation in strengthening community empowerment, so that participation is carried out not only for material purposes, but also socially for the common good.

Based on the results of data processing that has been done, it was found that the local wisdom variable (Y1) has a significant effect on the Sustainable tourism development variable (Y2) and is indicated by a positive path coefficient of 0.739 with a t-statistic value of 6.381 (greater than 1.96). This shows that Ho is rejected, which means the hypothesis is proven by showing a significant and positive influence between the variable local wisdom (Y1) on the variable Sustainable tourism development (Y2), so the higher the level of public understanding of local wisdom, the more sustainable performance will also increase. Tourism village or Sustainable tourism development (Y2). The results in this study are supported by the results of Suharto's research (2016) which provides an overview of the high level of understanding by the public in the form of local wisdom will significantly improve the performance of the tourism industry's sustainability, this is influenced by the level of concern and desire to achieve common goals, which will provide better results than planned. In Rukini (2015) the importance of growing a sense of responsibility and a sense of belonging within the community will be able to increase the desire to participate in building sustainable tourism. Tourist objects do not only belong to a few people or groups, but are owned by the people who live, know and make a living in these attractions.

Based on the results of data processing that has been done, it was found that the Community empowerment variable (X1) has a significant effect on the Sustainable tourism development variable (Y2) through the mediation of the local wisdom variable (Y1). The mediation results of the local wisdom variable (Y1) are indicated by a positive path coefficient of 0.621 with a t-statistic value of 5.082 (greater than 1.96). This shows that Ho is rejected, which means the hypothesis is proven by showing a significant and positive mediating effect between the local wisdom variable (Y1) on the Sustainable tourism development variable (Y2). So it can be seen that the higher the local wisdom variable (Y1), the higher the sustainability performance of the tourism industry. Communities are the main part in sustainable tourism, to improve the performance of the tourism industry, a sense of togetherness and belonging must be the most important thing before building a tourist attraction. Skilled human resources, having initiative is the key to the sustainability of tourist attractions, so that without community participation, sustainable tourism will be difficult to achieve (Rizkianto , 2018). There are many factors that affect the sustainability of a tourist attraction, not only from the people but also other factors such as natural wealth, culture, foreign investment, and other things that have not been studied in this study. The limitations in this study became an opportunity for the research team to carry out further research, so that a lot of similar literature is needed in the process of supporting future activities.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The conclusion from the analysis and discussion in this study is that there is a positive and significant relationship between the research variables together. The first variable is community empowerment on local wisdom, the second variable is community empowerment on sustainable tourism development, and the third variable is mediation of local wisdom on community empowerment and sustainable tourism development. This study was conducted by collecting data from tourist villages in the Province of Bali. The presence of many tourist villages made the research team want to evaluate their activities and effectiveness. However, there are obstacles in obtaining accurate data. The difficulty of finding samples in this study was caused by various activities carried out by residents, so that the research took longer than planned. In addition, several tourist villages have not yet formed tourism awareness groups, which can make it easier for the community to gather to discuss plans and problems in the village.

Suggestions that can be given through this research are; first, collaboration with the government and village managers. In order to obtain more accurate data and facilitate access to Village managers, it is important to establish close cooperation with the local government and related parties. With the support of the government and village managers, the research team was able to obtain more complete data and easier access to information related to activities and problems in tourist villages. Second, the need to form a tourism awareness group. To overcome obstacles in sample collection and community participation, it is proposed that tourism awareness groups be formed in every tourist village. This group can be a forum for gathering the community and discussing various plans and problems in the village. With the existence of tourism awareness groups, community participation in research will be more organized and effective. Third, Provision of better data access. Governments can play an important role in providing the data needed for this research. In this regard, it is important to improve the data collection and processing system and make it more accessible to the research team. With better access to data, the research team will be able to produce a more accurate and in-depth analysis of local wisdom and sustainable tourism development in tourist villages.

Fourth, there is attention to the uniqueness and characteristics of each Village. Given that every village in the Province of Bali has its own unique culture and natural charm, it is important to pay special attention to this aspect in research. The research team needs to map and understand the uniqueness and characteristics of each village to produce recommendations and solutions that are appropriate to the local context. By implementing these developments, this research can become more comprehensive and provide a more significant contribution to the development of local wisdom and sustainable tourism in tourist villages in the province of Bali.

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